

Improving Teaching Quality in Science Education using Kolb's Learning Model and 5E Learning Model

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Abstract

The study investigated if Kolb's and 5E learning models could improve teachers' teaching quality in science education subjects such as biology, chemistry and physics. A sample of 298 students from 9 purposively selected secondary schools out of a population of 4,421 Senior Secondary II students from Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria was used for the study. The study adopted quasi experimental research design of pretest, posttest and non-equivalent type. The instrument used for data collection was Science Education Teaching Quality Inventory (SETQI) with reliability value of 0.83 using Cronbach Alpha. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation while the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The study revealed that there was significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM) [$F_{2, 98}=431.009, P<0.05$]. It was found that there was significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using KLM, 5ELM and DM [$F_{2, 97}=247.001, P<0.05$]. It was revealed that there was significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using KLM, 5ELM and DM [$F_{2, 100}=323.001, P<0.05$]. It was recommended among others that serving science teachers should employ the use of Kolb's and 5E learning models in other to enhance the quality of their teaching and invariably enhance students' learning quality in Science Education.

Keywords: Teaching quality, Science education, Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model.

Introduction

The development of any nation depends largely on the level of education attained by her citizens especially in the area of science and technology. Education is an instrument “par excellence” for effective national development (FRN, 2013). One channel through which this is achieved is science education at the secondary school level. Science is the knowledge obtained from the systematic study of the structure and behaviour of the physical world, especially by observing, measuring and experimenting and the development of theories to describe the results of these activities (Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017). Science education cultivates students’ curiosity about the world and enhances scientific thinking. Nations that are said to be developed and largely considered as civilised have achieved that status through purposeful scientific education of their citizens (Ajayi, 2017). In cognizance with the importance of science and technology, science subjects such as biology, chemistry and physics are taught in senior secondary schools in Nigeria to produce individuals who will be able to live effectively in the modern age of science and technology and contribute to the development of the nation (FRN, 2013). Despite the importance of science education to mankind and the efforts of the researchers to improve on its teaching and learning, the teaching and learning quality of science education remains poor in Nigeria. The quality of education depends on the quality of educational input and output in its entirety.

High quality teaching and learning is central to raising standards in schools and to addressing under achievement. Teaching quality focuses on instructional inputs, instructional outputs, or the relationship between the two. Inputs for teaching quality focus how the instructor uses materials, interactions, and instructional process to change students’ behaviour; whereas instructional outputs focus on how student behaviours and

accomplishments such as achievement of learning outcomes vary by instructor. According to Cihanoglu (2012) quality teaching is an effective instruction that promotes excellence and students’ learning outcome through best-practices. The author further opines that teaching practices based on high standards of instruction and student engagement can be described as quality teaching. Quality teaching is focused on raising student achievement. Therefore, teachers need to maintain high quality teaching since quality teaching is essential for quality learning.

It is regrettable that there is a public outcry due to poor teaching quality of science education subjects such as biology, chemistry and physics as evidenced by WAEC Chief Examiner’s report in the recent years (WAEC Chief Examiner, 2017/2018). The report shows that the teaching quality of science subject is poor and in turn only few students obtained the minimum of five credits in biology, physics and chemistry respectively which are considered as one of the requirements to study science related disciplines in tertiary institutions. Most of the failures recorded in science education subjects have been attributed to inadequate exposure of students to activities, inadequate preparation, and inability to comprehend questions, and poor teaching and learning quality (Balarabe, 2016). Consequently, Adewale (2016) opines that poor teaching quality in biology; chemistry and physics in secondary schools are attributed to poor teaching methods. The author further opines that teaching methods such as lecture method, discussion method, field trip method and demonstration method adopted by science teachers have affected the teaching quality of science education. Adedayo (2015) noted that discussion method is popular in teaching of science education in secondary schools in Nigeria. The author further added that discussion method has received a lot of criticisms from different scholars

such as Olorundare (2014) and Haruna (2016). Discussion method is said to be teacher-centered as it does not involve the learners' active participation. These have led to teachers not exposing the students to meaningful learning and this at the same time has made students to perceive science education subjects such as biology, chemistry and physics as abstract and difficult concepts to understand.

Studies by Usman (2011), Olorunyomi (2013) and Ajayi (2019) revealed that students' negative attitude towards science, and teacher related factors such as poor teaching methods such as discussion method are some of the factors that could also affect the teaching quality of science education. By implication, poor method of teaching invariably translates to poor teaching quality. Therefore, teachers need to use a broad range of innovative teaching strategies to meet the needs of quality learning. Hence, science teachers should adopt innovative strategies that would enable the students to understand whatever science concepts, topics or principle that are being taught to improve the teaching and learning quality of science education. Consequently, This calls for the need to find innovative strategies such as Kolb's and 5E learning models that have the potential to equip learners to think about their cognition, monitor their learning activities and evaluate the results of these activities thereby improving learning and teaching quality. Kolb's learning model is an instructional tool meant for understanding the process of learning through four components of learning experiences.

Kolb's learning model shows how experience is translated through reflection into concepts. They are used in turn as guide for active experimentation and the choice of new experience (Kolb, 1984). Kolb (1984) developed the four components of the learning model which includes concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization and

active experimentation. The first stage of Kolb's learning model is where the learner actively experiences an activity such as lab-session or field work. The second stage reflective observation (RO) is when the learner consciously reflects back on that experience. The third stage is abstract conceptualization (AC) is where the learner attempts to conceptualize a theory or model of what is observed. The fourth stage active Experimentation (AE) is where the learner tries to plan how to test a model or theory, that is, planning for a forthcoming experience as shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1: The Kolb's Learning Model (Kolb, 1984)

These four stages or components guide the teacher on how to carry out the classroom instruction. The steps in the use of Kolb's model, exposes students to experiences and involvement in concrete learning situations. These enable them to think and deduce new strategy of achieving the same purpose (Umeano & Adimora, 2011). In this regard, experimentation and problem solving that present learners with option and critical thinking for action, are likely to be more successful in promoting sustainable knowledge, and skill.

5E learning model consists of five cognitive stages of learning that comprise engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate as shown in Figure 2.

Fig 2: The 5E Learning Model (Evan, 2010)

5E learning model is an instructional model of structuring a science lesson which is based upon constructivist approach to teaching (Evans, 2010). It is a recursive model of distinctive cognitive stages of learning that include; engage, explore, explain, elaborate and evaluate. Each phase or stage has a specific function and contributes to the teacher's coherent instruction, as well as the learners' formulation of a better understanding of scientific knowledge, attitudes, and skills (Bybee, 2012). 5E learning model involves learning something new, or attempting to understand something familiar in greater depth. It is not a linear process. In trying to make sense of things, students use both their prior experience and the first-hand knowledge gained from new explorations (Newby, 2014). Studies by Güneş (2017); Wilder and Shuttleworth (2014) have revealed that Kolb's learning model and 5E learning model respectively significantly enhances learners' learning outcome basic science and biology respectively when compared with conventional teaching method. It is on this note that, this study investigated if Kolb's and 5E learning models could improve teaching quality in Science Education.

Purpose of the Study

Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. determine the effect of Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method on teaching quality of biology teacher as assessed by students;

2. determine the effect of Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method on teaching quality of chemistry teacher as assessed by students; and
3. determine the effect of Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method on teaching quality of physics teacher as assessed by students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean teaching quality scores differences among biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method?
2. What are the mean teaching quality scores differences among chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method?
3. What are the mean teaching quality scores differences among physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of

physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method.

Research Design and Procedure

The study adopted a quasi-experimental non-randomized pre-test, post-test control group design. The study area was Makurdi Local Government Area (LGA) of Benue State, Nigeria. The population for this study comprised all Senior Secondary two (SSII) biology, chemistry and physics students numbering 4,421 from all the 114 approved Senior Secondary Schools in Makurdi Local Government Area. The sample of this study was made up of 298 Senior Secondary two (SSII) students comprising 99 biology students, 98 chemistry students and 101 physics students that were purposively drawn from 9 schools in Makurdi Local Government Areas of Benue State. One instrument known as Science Education Teaching Quality Inventory (SETQI) developed by the researchers was used in this study. SETQI is the researcher made 25-item questionnaire which was intended to help students assess the extent of their teachers teaching quality in science education. The instrument is a 4-point Likert-rating scale with 4 response options. The options are Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), and Low Extent (LE). SETQI is a 4-Likert scale with number indicators as 4 (Very High Extent), 3 (High Extent), 2 (Moderate Extent) and 1 (Low Extent)

Science Education Teaching Quality Inventory (SETQI) and the instructional packages (lesson plans) were face validated by presenting them to two experts in Science Education and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Mathematics and Science Education, Benue State University, Makurdi. The items were scrutinized by these experts. Corrections

arising from these experts were used to review the SETQI and the instructional packages. SETQI was trial-tested to establish the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.83 using Cronbach Alpha. One intact class from each of the nine sampled schools was selected using simple random sampling.

Three intact classes were assigned randomly to experimental group I (each of the three classes were taught biology, chemistry and physics concepts respectively using Kolb's learning model). In the same vein, three intact classes were also assigned randomly to experimental group II (each of the three classes were taught biology, chemistry and physics concepts respectively using 5E learning model). Likewise, three intact classes were assigned randomly to control group (each of the three classes were taught the same biology, chemistry and physics concepts respectively using discussion method). The Science Education Teaching Quality Inventory (SETQI) was administered as pre-test to the intact classes. This took place in the first week before teaching commenced. After six weeks of 12 periods of teaching, the same test instruments were administered as post-test though reshuffled. Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of the collected data were used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Results

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and null hypotheses.

Research Question One

What are the mean teaching quality scores differences among biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method? The answer to research question one is presented on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Teaching Quality and Standard Deviation Scores as Assessed by Students Taught Biology using KLM, 5ELM and DM

Group	N	PRE- SETQI		POST- SETQI		Mean Gain within Group
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Kolb's Model	32	1.27	0.18	3.74	0.21	2.47
Discussion	34	1.23	0.19	2.11	0.20	0.88
Mean diff. between Groups		0.04		1.63		1.59
5E Model	33	1.26	0.17	3.70	0.23	2.44
Discussion	34	1.23	0.19	2.11	0.20	0.88
Mean diff. between Groups		0.03		1.59		1.56
Kolb's Model	32	1.27	0.18	3.74	0.21	2.47
5E Model	33	1.26	0.17	3.70	0.23	2.44
Mean diff. between Groups		0.01		0.04		0.03

Table 1 reveals the mean teaching quality and standard deviation scores as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM) on a paired comparative basis. The data in Table 1 show that the overall mean teaching quality differences between biology teachers as assessed by students in KLM and DM groups was 1.59 in favour of biology teachers that taught students using KLM. This implies that biology teachers that taught using KLM had higher teaching quality than biology teachers that taught using DM. Similarly, the overall mean teaching quality differences between biology teachers as assessed by students in 5ELM and DM groups was 1.56 in favour of biology teachers that taught biology using 5ELM. This implies that biology teachers that taught students using 5ELM

had higher teaching quality than biology teachers that taught using DM. In the same vein, the overall mean teaching quality difference between biology teachers as assessed by students in KLM and 5ELM groups was 0.03. This difference though small is in favour of biology teachers that taught biology using KLM. This implies that biology teachers that taught using KLM had slightly higher teaching quality than biology teachers that taught students using 5ELM.

Research Question Two

What are the mean teaching quality scores differences among chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method? The answer to research question two is presented on Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Teaching Quality and Standard Deviation Scores as Assessed by Students Taught Chemistry using KLM, 5ELM and DM

Group	N	PRE- SETQI		POST- SETQI		Mean Gain within Group
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Kolb's Model	33	1.38	0.22	3.86	0.15	2.48
Discussion	33	1.33	0.20	2.16	0.14	0.83
Mean diff. between Groups		0.05		1.70		1.65
5E Model	32	1.36	0.17	3.83	0.18	2.47
Discussion	33	1.33	0.20	2.16	0.14	0.83
Mean diff. between Groups		0.03		1.67		1.64
Kolb's Model	33	1.38	0.22	3.86	0.15	2.48
5E Model	32	1.36	0.17	3.83	0.18	2.47
Mean diff. between Groups		0.02		0.03		0.01

Table 2 reveals the mean teaching quality and standard deviation scores as assessed by students taught chemistry using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM) on a paired comparative basis. The data in Table 1 show that the overall mean teaching quality differences between chemistry teachers as assessed by students in KLM and DM groups was 1.65 in favour of chemistry teachers that taught students using KLM. This implies that chemistry teachers that taught using KLM had higher teaching quality than chemistry teachers that taught using DM. Similarly, the overall mean teaching quality differences between chemistry teachers as assessed by students in 5ELM and DM groups was 1.64 in favour of chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using 5ELM. This implies that chemistry teachers that taught using 5ELM had

higher teaching quality than chemistry teachers that taught students using DM. In the same vein, the overall mean teaching quality difference between chemistry teachers as assessed by students in KLM and 5ELM groups was 0.01. This difference though small is in favour of chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using KLM. This implies that chemistry teachers that taught using KLM had slightly higher teaching quality than chemistry teachers that taught using 5ELM.

Research Question Three

What are the mean teaching quality scores differences among physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method? The answer to research question three is contained on Table 3.

Table 3: Mean Teaching Quality and Standard Deviation Scores as Assessed by Students Taught Physics using KLM, 5ELM and DM

Group	N	PRE- SETQI		POST- SETQI		Mean Gain within Group
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Kolb's Model	34	1.21	0.12	3.87	0.14	2.66
Discussion	35	1.19	0.10	2.21	0.16	1.02
Mean diff. between Groups		0.02		1.66		1.64
5E Model	32	1.20	0.13	3.84	0.17	2.64
Discussion	35	1.19	0.10	2.21	0.16	1.02
Mean diff. between Groups		0.01		1.63		1.62
Kolb's Model	34	1.21	0.12	3.87	0.14	2.66
5E Model	32	1.20	0.13	3.84	0.17	2.64
Mean diff. between Groups		0.01		0.03		0.02

Table 3 reveals the mean teaching quality and standard deviation scores as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM) on a paired comparative basis. The data in Table 1 show that the overall mean teaching quality differences between physics teachers as assessed by students in KLM and DM groups was 1.64 in favour of physics teachers that taught students using KLM. This implies that physics teachers that taught students using KLM had higher teaching quality than physics teachers that taught using DM. Similarly, the overall mean teaching quality differences between physics teachers as assessed by students in 5ELM and DM groups was 1.62 in favour of physics teachers that taught physics using 5ELM. This implies that physics teachers that

taught using 5ELM had higher teaching quality than physics teachers that taught using DM. In the same vein, the overall mean teaching quality difference between physics teachers as assessed by students in KLM and 5ELM groups was 0.02. This difference though small is in favour of physics teachers that taught physics using KLM. This implies that physics teachers that taught using KLM had slightly higher teaching quality than physics teachers that taught students using 5ELM.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method. The test for hypothesis one is presented on Table 4.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result for Mean Teaching Quality Scores as Assessed by Students Taught Biology using KLM, 5ELM and DM

Source	Type III sum of square	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared
Corrected model	2809.991	3	340.005	218.006	.000	0.81
Intercept	1919.001	1	1919.001	158.009	.000	0.05
TPrSETQI	182.101	1	182.101	151.001	.000	0.42
Group	2910.001	2	2910.001	431.009	.000	0.37
Error	429.390	93	13.830			
Total	211005.001	99				
Corrected Total	4901.100	98				

a. R squared = .124 (Adjusted R Squared= .221)

Table 4 presents the ANCOVA result for mean teaching quality scores of biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM). The data in Table 4 reveal that the observed mean difference in the teaching quality scores among the biology teachers was significant [$F_{2, 98}=431.009$, $P<0.05$]. Hence, the null

hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using KLM, 5ELM and DM was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method.

Table 5: Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for Mean Teaching Quality Scores as Assessed by Students' Taught Biology using KLM, 5ELM and DM

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
KLM	DM	9.001*	4.77	.000
5ELM	DM	10.001*	4.04	.000
5ELM	KLM	1.000	4.23	.102

Table 5 shows Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for mean teaching quality scores of biology teachers as assessed by students taught biology using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM). The results reveal that the mean teaching quality difference (I-J) between biology teachers that taught biology using KLM and those that taught biology using DM is 9.001* and this is significant at $p<0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between biology teachers that taught biology using KLM and those that

taught biology using DM in favour of biology teacher that taught biology using KLM. Likewise, the results reveal that the mean teaching quality difference (I-J) between biology teachers that taught biology using 5ELM and those that taught biology using DM is 10.001* and this is significant at $p<0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between biology teachers that taught biology using 5ELM and those that taught biology using DM in favour of biology teacher that taught biology using 5ELM. However, the paired comparison of biology teachers that taught

biology using 5ELM and KLM showed a mean teaching quality difference of 1.000 and this is not significant at $p > 0.05$. This indicates no significant difference in the

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught

mean teaching quality scores between biology teachers that taught biology using KLM and 5ELM

chemistry using Kolb’s learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method. The test for hypothesis two is presented on Table 6.

Table 6: ANCOVA Result for Mean Teaching Quality Scores as Assessed by Students Taught Chemistry using KLM, 5ELM and DM

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared
Corrected model	1809.990	3	312.009	175.001	.000	0.74
Intercept	1530.001	1	1530.001	179.001	.000	0.05
TPrSETQI	291.001	1	291.001	99.002	.000	0.60
Group	1574.905	2	1574.905	247.001	.000	0.43
Error	587.010	92	19.891			
Total	199997.001	98				
Corrected Total	3900.410	97				

a. R squared = .044 (Adjusted R Squared= .099) Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 6 presents the ANCOVA result for mean teaching quality scores of chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using Kolb’s learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM). The data in Table 6 reveal that the observed mean difference in the teaching quality scores among the chemistry teachers was significant [$F_{2, 97} = 247.001, P < 0.05$]. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no

significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using KLM, 5ELM and DM was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using Kolb’s learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method.

Table 7: Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for Mean Teaching Quality Scores as Assessed by Students’ Taught Chemistry using KLM, 5ELM and DM

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
KLM	DM	7.778*	3.89	.000
5ELM	DM	8.878*	3.64	.000
5ELM	KLM	1.100	3.38	.237

Table 7 shows Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for mean teaching quality scores of chemistry teachers as assessed by students taught chemistry using Kolb’s learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and

discussion method (DM). The results reveal that the mean teaching quality difference (I-J) between chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using KLM and those that taught chemistry using DM is 7.778* and this is

significant at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using KLM and those that taught chemistry using DM in favour of chemistry teacher that taught chemistry using KLM. Likewise, the results reveal that the mean teaching quality difference (I-J) between chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using 5ELM and those that taught chemistry using DM is 8.878* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using 5ELM and those that taught chemistry using DM in favour of chemistry teacher that taught chemistry using 5ELM.

However, the paired comparison of chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using 5ELM and KLM showed a mean teaching quality difference of 1.100 and this is not significant at $p > 0.05$. This indicates no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between chemistry teachers that taught chemistry using KLM and 5ELM.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method. The test for hypothesis three is presented on Table 8.

Table 8: ANCOVA Result for Mean Teaching Quality Scores as Assessed by Students Taught Physics using KLM, 5ELM and DM

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared
Corrected model	3109.001	3	502.001	212.001	.000	0.76
Intercept	1577.001	1	1577.001	177.001	.000	0.05
TPrSETQI	276.001	1	276.001	89.009	.000	0.60
Group	1587.905	2	1587.905	323.001	.000	0.43
Error	789.290	95	23.090			
Total	108998.009	101				
Corrected Total	3601.490	100				

b. R squared = .174 (Adjusted R Squared= .201) Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 8 presents the ANCOVA result for mean teaching quality scores of physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM). The data in Table 8 reveal that the observed mean difference in the teaching quality scores among the physics teachers was significant [$F_{2,100} = 323.001, P < 0.05$]. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant

difference in the mean teaching quality scores of physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using KLM, 5ELM and DM was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores of physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method

Table 9: Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for Mean Teaching Quality Scores as Assessed Students' Taught Physics using KLM, 5ELM and DM

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
KLM	DM	10.578*	3.56	.000
5ELM	DM	11.578*	3.61	.000
5ELM	KLM	1.000	3.59	.201

Table 9 shows Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for mean teaching quality scores of physics teachers as assessed by students taught physics using Kolb's learning model (KLM), 5E learning model (5ELM) and discussion method (DM). The results reveal that the mean teaching quality difference (I-J) between physics teachers that taught physics using KLM and those that taught physics using DM is 10.578* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between physics teachers that taught physics using KLM and those that taught physics using DM in favour of physics teacher that taught physics using KLM. Likewise, the results reveal that the mean teaching quality difference (I-J) between physics teachers that taught physics using 5ELM and those that taught physics using DM is 11.578* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between physics teachers that taught physics using 5ELM and those that taught physics using DM in favour of physics teacher that taught physics using 5ELM. However, the paired comparison of physics teachers that used 5ELM and KLM showed a mean teaching quality difference of 1.000 and this is not significant at $p > 0.05$. This indicates no significant difference in the mean teaching quality scores between physics teachers that taught physics using KLM and 5ELM.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that the difference in the teaching quality scores among biology, chemistry and physics teachers respectively as assessed by students taught biology concept, chemistry concepts and physics concepts respectively using Kolb's learning model, 5E learning model and discussion method was statistically significant. The post-hoc comparison for the teaching quality scores among biology, chemistry and physics teachers respectively revealed that teachers that taught biology concept, chemistry concepts and physics concepts respectively using Kolb's learning model had significantly higher teaching quality than their counterparts that taught the same biology concept, chemistry concepts and physics concepts respectively using discussion method. Likewise, the findings of the study revealed that teachers that taught biology concept, chemistry concepts and physics concepts using 5E learning model had significantly higher teaching quality

than their counterparts that taught the same biology concept, chemistry concepts and physics concepts respectively using discussion method.

However, the post-hoc comparison for the teaching quality among the teachers further revealed that the difference in the teaching quality scores between teachers as assessed by students taught biology concept, chemistry concepts and physics concepts respectively using Kolb's learning model and 5E learning model was not statistically significant. The likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that both Kolb's and 5E learning models helped the learners in the assimilation, accommodation and the reflective abstraction processes involved in subjective cognitive construction of knowledge when compared to discussion method. Furthermore, the models exposed the students to various learning experiences from which students made reflective reasoning/observation and as such acquire the necessary skills involved in the learning process and the learning models also helped the learners' foster intrinsic interest, and deep engrossment in activities when compared to discussion method. This finding agrees with Güneş (2017) who revealed that students learning outcome improved significantly in basic science when taught using Kolb's learning model compared to those taught using conventional teaching method. This finding also agrees with Wilder and Shuttleworth (2014) who revealed that use of the 5E learning model is more successful in term of improving learning of biology than the lecture teaching methods.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of Kolb's and 5E learning models improved teachers' teaching quality in biology, physics, and chemistry respectively than the use of discussion method. Invariably, this implies that Kolb's and 5E learning models respectively are rewarding to teachers and students in-terms of improving teacher's teaching quality and invariably improving students learning quality in science education subjects such as biology, chemistry and physics

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Serving science teachers should employ the use of Kolb's and 5E learning models in other to enhance the quality of their teaching and invariably enhance

- students learning quality in Science Education.
2. Ministry of Education and professional bodies such as Association of Science Educators (ASE) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize conferences or seminars and workshops to popularize and sensitize science teachers on the integration of Kolb's and 5E learning models in teaching biology, chemistry and physics concepts so as to improve their teaching quality.

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